

Minutes EB23-01
Meeting of the SeqCode Executive Board
3 February 2023 @ 7h00 (EST)

Attendance

Executive Board (EB)

Maria Chuvochina (MC)	- Chair Reconciliation Commission
Phil Hugenholtz (PH)	- Member without portfolio
Kostas Konstantinidis (KK)	- Chair, Standards Working Group
Anna-Louise Reysenbach (ALR)	- Vice Chair
Luis Miguel Rodriguez (LMR)	- Chair, Registry Working Group
Iain Sutcliffe (IS)	- Chair, Legislative Commission
Fanus Venter (FV)	- Secretary
Fengping Wang (FW)	- Member without portfolio
Barny Whitman (BW)	- Chair

Other attending

Alexander Probst (AP)	- Member of the former Steering Committee
-----------------------	---

1. Welcome and introductions

BW welcomed all the members of the Executive Board as well as members of the former SeqCode Steering Committee (replaced by the newly elected SeqCode Committee from the 1st Jan 2023) and asked them to introduce themselves. It is noted that most of the members of the SeqCode Steering Committee sent their apologies as the time of the meeting was rather inconvenient for them.

2. Additions to the Agenda

MC asked for the funding received from ISME to be discussed.
MC asked to discuss our response to the IJSEM editorial on the use of the SeqCode to describe new taxa.

3. Establishment of meeting schedule

After some discussion it was decided that the same time slot will be used and that meetings will be held every second month. This arrangement will be revisited should the need arise. Urgent matters that need attention between meetings will be dealt via email. Commissions and working groups could use the alternative months for their meetings. FV will send out a poll to determine the date of the next EB meeting.

4. SeqCode Steering Committee report

The EB has invited all members of the SeqCode Steering Committee who are not part of the EB to join the first meeting to ensure a smooth transition of the committee's outstanding activities to the EB. As many of them could not attend, FV will contact and thank them for their participation and share the minutes of this meeting. All former members will be requested to inform the EB of any additional matters that they believe should be addressed by the EB.

It was decided that MC will take over the liaison with Sabine van Wegen from the ISME Office to update the SeqCode information on the ISME website.

5. Reports from Commissions and Working Groups

The commissions and working groups still need to hold their first meetings.

6. Approval of co-opted members

It was decided that the co-opted members of the working groups will be approved by voting via email once their names and a short CV have been shared with the EB.

LMR and KK to share the names and short CVs with FV. FV to send out a ballot to the EB.

7. Reporting to larger membership

Minutes

After some discussion it was decided that the minutes will be circulated by FV to the EB for their comments within a set time period. Once the minutes will be approved by the EB members who attended the meeting, it will be uploaded on the ISME website. The broader SeqCode community will be alerted of the posting of the minutes by email, twitter or a message on Slack.

News

New items will be posted on the ISME website and also reflected on the registry website. News items should be shared with MC, who will post it after consultation with the EB via email. Important news items will be incorporated into a newsletter for the broader community twice a year. The person responsible for the newsletter will be nominated at the next meeting. A formal report on the activities of the SeqCode will be prepared in January 2024 for submission to ISME communications.

Discussions

It was decided that the EB does not want to spend money on Slack if there are alternative open source options. FV with the assistance from AP will investigate the creation of the channels for the SeqCode EB, commissions and working groups on rocket.chat platform (<https://www.rocket.chat/>). The information on the existing Slack channels will be migrated when EB will decide on the usage of alternative platform. LMR offered to host the data. A final decision to move the discussion channels for the wider community to rocket.chat will be made once EB members have tested the new platform and the hosting has been sorted.

Website

MC will take responsibility for the SeqCode-relevant news and information update on the ISME website.

8. ISME funding

ISME provided the SeqCode with funding of €5000 for 2023. It was decided that it should be used for the development of the registry. MLR will provide a proposal on how best to spend the funding.

9. Priorities for Year One

a. Funding of the Registry

EB members were asked to look for possible funding sources to support the activities of the SeqCode and the development of the Registry. KK and BW will contact Brian Hedlund to follow-up on the NFS' RCN funding. LMR to investigate the EU COST Action funding, and FW to look for Chinese funding opportunities.

b. Membership expansion / How to publicize the SeqCode

BW and ALR will write a piece for ASM's Microcosm newsletter to create awareness of the SeqCode. This could also serve as a way to clarify issues brought up in the editorial published in the IJSEM Volume 72, Issue 12, 2022. [redacted] The EB welcomes proposals to work with the ICSP and avoid conflicts.

c. Presentations at local / international meetings

The best promotion of the SeqCode will be when EB and other members include information on the SeqCode as part of their conference and/or seminar presentations. Based on the current slides available, ALR will create two slides for general use to promote the use of the SeqCode. The possibility of a SeqCode Wikipedia page should also be investigated.

The meeting was adjourned.

Action items

1. FV to send out a poll to determine the date of the next meeting.
2. FV to contact all members of the SeqCode Steering Committee who are not part of the EB to thank them for their participation and share the minutes of this meeting.
3. MC to liaise with Sabine to update the SeqCode information on the ISME website.
4. LMR and KK to share the names and short CVs of the proposed co-opted members of their working groups with FV.
5. FV to send out a ballot to the EB to vote for approval of co-opted members of the working groups.
6. FV to circulate the minutes to the EB for their comments within a set time period.
7. MC to arrange for the posting of the minutes on the ISME webpage.
8. MC and FV to alert the broader community of the posting of the minutes via email, twitter and slack.
9. MC to have news items posted on the ISME website after consultation with the EB.
10. EB to decide on person responsible for the newsletter at the next meeting.
11. EB to prepare a formal report on the activities of the SeqCode for submission to ISME communications after January 2024.
12. FV with the assistance from AP to investigate the creation of a channel for the SeqCode EB, commissions and working groups on rocket.chat.
13. MLR to provide a proposal on how best to spend the ISME funding for the development of the Registry.
14. KK and BW to contact Brian Hedlund to follow-up on the NFS' RCN funding.
15. LMR to investigate the EU COST Action funding.
16. FW to look for Chinese funding opportunities.
17. BW and ALR will write a piece for ASM's Microcosm newsletter.
18. Redacted
19. ALR to create slides for general use to promote the use of the SeqCode.

Minutes prepared by FV, February 04, 2023

Approved February 10, 2023